

FREE AND INFORMED CONSENT TERMS

Introduction

The Blekinge Institute of Technology (BTH, Sweden) is carrying out a research project that has as one of its main objectives improving agile team building, so that the set of technical skills, experiences and personalities in teams becomes balanced ; This balance leads to harmonious and productive teams, where team members can grow and develop. To achieve this objective, we need your help by providing data through the questionnaire, available here.

Participation in this research is voluntary.

The data you provide will be anonymous to everyone working on the research project and elsewhere; the connection between your personal data and your responses will only be known to a BTH researcher, who will archive the data in a secure location. The data will be destroyed upon completion of the research.

There are no right or wrong answers, please provide your immediate impressions. This questionnaire takes approximately 40 to 45 minutes to complete. Note that underlined words/phrases are described in more detail by hovering over them.

We would like to thank you for your time and willingness to participate.

I confirm that (please tick the box as appropriate):

1. I had the opportunity to ask questions about the project and my participation.*

Yes

two. I voluntarily agree to participate in the project.*

Yes

I understand that I can withdraw at any time without giving reasons and that I will not
3. I will be penalized for withdrawing, nor will I be asked why I withdrew. *

Yes

Procedures regarding confidentiality were clearly explained (e.g.
4. example, use of names, pseudonyms, anonymization of data, etc.) for me. *

Yes

5. If applicable, separate consent terms for interviews, audio, video or other forms of data collection were explained and provided to me. *

Yes

The use of data in research, publications, sharing and archiving was
6. explained to me. *

Yes

7. I understand that a BTH researcher will only have access to this data if they agree to preserve the confidentiality of the data and if they agree to the terms I have specified in this form. *

Yes

8. I understand that the data I provided as part of this research may be used in reports, publications and other research outputs; however, my anonymity will be maintained. *

Yes

9. I, along with the researcher(s), agree to sign and date this consent form. *

Yes

Demographic details

1. Which of the following best describes your primary role in your organization? *

Product Manager

Program Manager

Functional manager

Product Owner

Team leader

Internal coach/mentor

Expert / Technical Lead User Experience Lead

Domain Expert

Continuous integration engineer

Scrum master

Developer

Tester

User experience designer

Architect

Other

-

Describe:

(Mandatory)

2. How many years of experience do you have in the software industry? *

3. How many years of experience do you have in your current organization? *

4. How many members work with you in your current team? *

5. What is your team ID? *

6. Which country are you most familiar with, whether by virtue of citizenship, length of residence or acculturation? *

7. How old are you? *

8. What is your gender? *

Female

Male

Other

Questionnaire part 1

The following pages contain sentences that describe people's behavior. Please use the rating scale next to each sentence to describe how accurately each statement describes you. Describe yourself as you generally are now, not as you want to be in the future.

Describe honestly how you see yourself in relation to other people you know of the same sex as you and approximately the same age. Your responses will be kept absolutely confidential. There are no right or wrong answers, provide your immediate impressions.

Note that most sentences are self-explanatory. Phrases or words that require an explanation have been underlined and a brief description can be found by hovering the mouse over them. Please **read each sentence carefully** and do not hesitate to ask the researcher responsible for your session if you require additional explanations. *

		Very	mode	Nor	mode	Very
		Print	ada	pre	ada	Pre
		cis	me	cis	me	cis
		o	nte		nte	o
			Print	One M	Precise	
			cis	im	o	
			o	pre		

				cis o		
1.	I worry about things	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
two.	I make friends easily	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
3.	I have a fertile imagination. _____	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
4.	I trust others	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
5.	Complete tasks successfully	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
6.	I get angry easily	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
7.	I love parties with lots of people	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
8.	I believe in the importance of art	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
9.	I use third parties for personal purposes.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
10.	I like order	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
11.	I often feel sad	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
12.	I take charge of situations.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
13.	I experience my emotions intensely.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
14.	I make people feel welcome.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
15.	I keep my promises.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
16.	I have difficulty approaching other people. ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ					
17.	I'm always busy...	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
18.	I prefer variety to routine	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
19.	I like challenges.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
20.	I am committed to work	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
		Very Im pre cis o	Mode radame nte Im pre cis o	Nor pre cis o Huh m im pre cis o	Mode radame nte Pre eci only	Very Pre eci only

21. I like exaggerations.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
22. I love adrenaline	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
23. I like reading about complex subjects.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
24. I believe I am better than others.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
25. I am always prepared.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
26. Panic easily.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
27. I radiate joy.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
28. I tend to vote for liberal political candidates.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
29. I have compassion for the homeless	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
30. I do things without thinking.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
31. I'm afraid of the worst.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
32. I feel comfortable around people.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
33. I enjoy high flights in my imagination.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
34. I believe that others have good intentions	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
35. I excel in the things I do	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
36. I get angry easily	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
37. I talk to a lot of people at parties.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
38. I see beauty in things that other people may not notice.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
39. Cheating to gain advantages.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
40. I often forget to put things back in their proper place.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
41. I don't like myself.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
42. I try to lead others.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
43. I feel other people's emotions.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
44. I put myself in other people's shoes (empathy).	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
45. I speak the truth.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
46. I'm afraid of drawing attention to myself.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
47. I am always active.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
48. I prefer to work with things that I am familiar with.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
49. I yell at people.				

		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
		Very Im pre cis o	Mode <small>radame</small> nte Im pre cis o	Nor pre cis o Huh m im pre cis o	Mode <small>radame</small> nte Pr eci <small>only</small>	Very Pr eci <small>only</small>
50. Do more than expected of me.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
51. I rarely exaggerate		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
52. I look for adventure.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
53. I avoid philosophical discussions.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
54. I think intensely about myself		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
55. I carry out my plans.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
56. I often feel overwhelmed.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
57. I have a lot of fun		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
58. I believe that there is no absolute truth.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
59. I feel compassion for those less well-off than me.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
60. I make hasty decisions.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
61. I am afraid of many things.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
62. I avoid contact with other people.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
63. I love daydreaming		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
64. I trust what people say.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
65. I handle my tasks calmly.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
66. I get bored easily.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
67. I prefer to be alone.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
68. I don't like poetry.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
69. I take advantage of others.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
70. I leave my room disorganized.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
71. I often feel like crap		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
72. I take control of things.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
73. I rarely notice my emotional reactions.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			
74. I am indifferent to the feelings of others.		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ	ÿ ÿ			

75. I break the rules	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
76. I just feel comfortable with my friends	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
77. I do different things in my free time.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
78. I don't like change.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
	Very Imprecise	Mode <small>radame</small> n te Imprecise	Norprecise <small>o</small> Huh m imprecise <small>o</small>	Mode <small>radame</small> n te Pr eci <small>only</small>	Very Precise <small>only</small>
79. I insult people.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
80. I only do the work necessary to survive.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
81. I easily resist temptations.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
82. I enjoy being reckless.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
83. I have difficulty understanding abstract ideas.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
84. I have an overestimated opinion of myself same.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
85. I waste my time.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
86. I feel like I am unable to handle things. ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ					
87. I love life.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
88. I tend to vote for conservative political candidates.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
89. I'm not interested in other people's problems.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
90. I rush to carry out activities.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
91. I get stressed easily	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
92. I keep others at a distance.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
93. I like to lose myself in my thoughts.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
94. I don't trust people.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
95. I know how to finish my activities. ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ					
96. I don't get angry easily	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
97. I avoid crowds.					

		ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
98.	I don't like going to art museums.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
99.	I obstruct other people's plans.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
100.	I leave my belongings nearby.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
101.	I feel comfortable with myself.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
102.	I look forward to others leading the way.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
103.	Don't understand people who get emotional.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
104.	I don't have time for others.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
105.	I don't keep my promises.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
106.	I'm not bothered by difficult social situations.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
107.	I would like to remain calm.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
108.	I am attached to conventional ways/ modes.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
		Very Imprecis o	Mode radame n te Im pre cis o	Norprecis o Huh m im pre cis o	Mode radame n te Pr eci only	Very Preci only
109.	I get revenge on people	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
110.	I dedicate little time and effort to my work.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
111.	I am able to control my desires.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
112.	I love action	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
113.	I'm not interested in theoretical discussions.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
114.	I boast my virtues.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
115.	I have difficulty starting tasks.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
116.	I stay calm under pressure.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				

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117	I see the positive side of life.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
118	I believe we should be tough on crime. ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ					
119	I try not to think about those in need.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
120	I act without thinking.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				

Please indicate to what degree you agree or disagree with the following statements *

		Disco strong rdo mind is	Disco rdo	No conco rdo no disk rdo	Conc order	Conc full order mind is
1.	I have the ability to be responsible, answerable, or accountable for something within my control.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
two.	I believe that I can accurately receive and interpret messages during communication.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
3.	I am confident that I can express doubts and raise objections to something.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
4.	Compared to others, I can work cohesively with a group of people to achieve a goal common.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
5.	Compared to others, I can work collaboratively with a group of people.	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				

Quiz part 2

This questionnaire emphasizes the shared perception among team members regarding organizational policies, practices, and behaviors of members. There are no right or wrong answers, provide your immediate impressions. *

		Even a lot o little o	Until one little o	In grade mode rado	In big by measure from the	in excellent measure from the
1.	How clear are you about what your team's goals are?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				

two.	How useful do you think these goals are?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
3.	To what extent do you agree with these objectives?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
4.	To what extent do you think your team's goals are clearly understood by other team members?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
5.	To what extent do you think other team members agree with these goals?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
6.	To what extent do you think your team's goals can actually be achieved?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
7.	Do you think these goals are worth it?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
8.	How do you think these goals are worth to the organization?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
9.	How do you think these goals hold true for society at large?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
10.	How realistic and achievable do you think these goals are?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
11.	How committed do you think your team members are to these goals?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
12.	Do your teammates provide useful ideas and practical help to enable you to do your job to the best of your ability?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
13.	Do you and your colleagues monitor each other to maintain a higher standard of work?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
14.	Team members are prepared to Question the basis of what the team is doing?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
15.	The team critically evaluates weaknesses in potential in what you are doing to achieve the best possible result?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
16.	Do team members build on each other's ideas to achieve the best possible result?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
17.	Is it a real concern among team members that the team achieve the highest standards of performance?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
18.	Does the team have clear criteria that members try to meet to achieve excellence as a team?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
19.	The team is always moving towards developing new answers	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
		Even a lot o little o	Until one little o	In grade mode rado	In big by measure from the	in great measure from the
20.	In this team, we dedicate the necessary time to develop new ideas	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
21.	Assistance for developing new ideas is available	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
22.	The team is open and receptive to change	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
23.	People on this team cooperate to help develop and apply new ideas	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
24.	People on this team are always looking for new ways to look at problems	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				

25.	Team members provide and share resources to help apply new ideas	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
26.	Team members provide practical support for new ideas and their application	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
27.	We share information generally within the team rather than keeping it to ourselves	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
28.	We have a "we're in this together" attitude	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
29.	We all influence each other	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
30.	People stay informed about work-related issues in the team	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
31.	People feel understood and accepted by each other	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
32.	Everyone's opinion is heard, even if it is a minority	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
33.	There are real attempts to share information across the team	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
34.	There is a lot of give and take	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
35.	We keep in regular contact with each other	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
36.	We interact frequently	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
37.	We keep in touch with each other as a team	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
38.	Team members meet frequently to talk formally and informally	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			

Please read the underlined sentences before answering the questions. You can find a description by hovering your mouse over a phrase. There are no right or wrong answers, provide your immediate impressions. *

		Even a lot o little o	Until one little o	In grade mode rado	In big and measure from the	in great to measure from the
1.	How mature is your team when it comes to coding?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
2.	How mature is your team when it comes to code review?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
3.	How mature is your team when it comes to leading technical solutions?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
4.	To what extent is your team involved in	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				

	Regarding coding?				
5.	How involved is your team when it comes to code review?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
6.	How good is your team at ensuring low technical debt associated with proprietary components?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
7.	How good is your team at ensuring a low number of serious code issues associated with the components you own?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
8.	How good is your team at ensuring adequate code coverage associated with your own components?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			

Quiz part 3

For this section, carefully read the scale description for each question. There are no right or wrong answers, provide your immediate impressions. *

		False	More fake how true deiro	Nor Green join o nor False	More Green join what False	Green join o
1.	Do development team members always share the same workspace?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
2.	Do development team members talk face-to-face whenever possible?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
3.	Team members share their difficulties and your progress in relation to the activities carried out in a clear and objective way?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
4.	Were all team members present during the daily meetings?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
5.	Do team members get along well with each other?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
6.	Do team members have all the knowledge necessary to develop intersecting sprint stories?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
7.	Authority in decision-making and Is leadership shared among team members?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
8.	Does the team adapt easily to changes that occur during the project?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ				
9.	There is an external agent interfering with how the					

	team performs its tasks?	ÿ ÿ ÿ ÿ			
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Additional comments

Are you interested in receiving the survey results?

ÿ Yes

ÿ No

What else would you like us to know? Any other information you would like to share? We would be happy to hear from you.

***Thank you very much for participating in this study!
We really appreciate your effort in helping us.***

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